

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE MAIN FUNCTIONS, FEATURES AND EFFECTIVENESS OF PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING

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Abstract

This article examines the effectiveness of using problematic situations in speech learning when learning foreign languages. The concept of problem-based learning is considered, the features of speech learning as an important language activity are revealed. The text pays considerable attention to the analysis of scientific literature related to the subject area, which gives the article a scientific character. In foreign language lessons, knowledge and the ability to calculate methodological foundations in building problem situations develops students' intellectual and creative abilities, forms solid and deep knowledge, skills, and also through the formation of their flexibility and skills, students can independently master new knowledge.

Keywords: problem-based, learning, ability, pedagogy, teacher, student, method, solution, skills.

The main problems in teaching a foreign language are that students cannot use their knowledge in conversation in real communication. In this regard, there is a need to create problematic situations in speech learning. A problematic situation serves as the central component of problem-based learning, giving rise to thoughts, addressing cognitive needs, and activating thinking, conditions are created for the formation of the correct configuration. Creating problematic situations that initiate the first moment of thinking is a crucial element in organizing the educational process, ensuring the development of genuine productive thinking and creative abilities among students. Research shows that the idea of problem-based learning is not new. Great teachers of the last century, such as Ya. A. Komensky, J. J. Rousseau, I. G. Pestalozzi, F. A. Disterweg, K. D. Ushinsky, were looking for ways to change the processes of developing students' thinking abilities. In the 1920s, the idea of problem-based learning developed rapidly and became widespread in educational practice.

The concept of problem-based learning in foreign pedagogy developed under the influence of the idea of J. Dewey. The American philosopher, educator, and psychologist in his work "How we Think" rejects traditional teaching and opposes students with active, individual practical abilities in solving problems. According to J. Dewey in his work 'How We Think,' thinking is the solution to problems [1].

In the second edition of this book, J. Dewey substantiates the psychological mechanism of students' ability to solve problems. According to him, students' problem-solving abilities are based on natural thought.

In addition, the American psychologist J. Bruner was involved in the development of the theory of problem-based learning, and his concept played a major role. According to the scientist, the most fundamental problem here is the structure of knowledge, which determines the direction of the student's development and consists of the necessary elements of the knowledge system.

These authors are brought closer: J. Dewey and J. Bruner emphasize the importance of a problem-based

approach to learning, recognizing that the purpose of learning is to develop logical thinking [2].

Since the mid-fifties of the last century, the concept of problem-based learning has gained prominence in Russian pedagogical literature.

The work of such Russian psychologists as S. L. Rubinstein, N.A. Menchinskaya, T. V. Kudryavtsev contributed to the increasing importance of the theory of problem-based learning. According to psychologists, the mental development of students is determined not only by the amount and volume of acquired knowledge, but also by the structure of the thought process, the system of logical operations, and mental activity.

In the pedagogical literature, there are a number of types of definitions of problem-based learning. We will show some of them below:

W. Okon defines problem-based learning: "Problem-based learning is a set of actions, such as the formation of problem situations, composing problems, providing students with necessary assistance in completing tasks, checking these solutions, and managing the process of consolidating and systematizing acquired knowledge" [3].

T. V. Kudryavtsev sees the essence of the process of problem-based learning in the fact that "The formulation of didactic tasks for students, their solution, lies in the fact that students have general knowledge and principles of solving problems."

V. T. Kudryavtsev defines problem-based learning as a type of developmental learning determined by a system of problem tasks, the complexity of which is at different levels. In the process of solving such tasks, students acquire ways of working together with teachers and, as a result of the general managerial actions of teachers, acquire new knowledge and methods of action. [4].

Now let's focus on the application of problem-based learning.

Makhmutov M. I. provides a generalized definition: "Problem-based learning is a form of developmental learning in which the development of a ready-made conclusion of science is combined with independent, systematic search activity of students." The systems of

designing methods are carried out taking into account the definition of the goal and the construction of the problematic principle.

Problem-based learning has its specific functions and features, as compiled by M. I. Makhmutov, divided into general and special ones.

General functions of problem-based learning include:

- Mastering the knowledge system, ways of thinking, and practical activities by students;
- Development of students' intelligence, i.e. the development of their creative abilities and cognition;
- Formation of students' dialectical thinking;
- Formation of comprehensive personality development.

Special functions of problem-based learning include:

- Using systems of logical approaches or individual methods of creative activity;
- Application of acquired knowledge in new situations and the ability to solve educational tasks;
- Mastering the methods of scientific research, solving practical problems and creative manifestation of clarity;
- Formation of motives for teaching socio-moral and cognitive needs [5].

Like other scientific theories, V. T. Kudryavtsev's theory of problem-based learning has its own explanatory apparatus. Also, scientists such as T. V. Kudryavtseva, I. Ya. Lerner, A.M. Matyushkin, M. I. Makhmutov give the following basic concepts of this theory: a problem situation, a learning problem, a problem problem, a problem question, a way to solve a problem situation.

In the search for data, students engage in active mental activity, such as analyzing evidence and identifying the causes of objects.

The structure of the problem problem is formed by three components: data information, requirement, and problem thinking.

The content of the problematic issue is analyzed in the works of such scientists as T. V. Kudryavtseva, M. I. Makhmutova, I. Ya. Lerner, T. A. Ilyina. After analyzing various definitions, we came to the conclusion: a problematic question – the student does not have a preliminary answer to this question; the student is looking for this answer on his own.

Unlike a simple question, a problematic question requires not only remembering something; it generates opposite situations and encourages the search for new unknown knowledge.

According to V. T. Kudryavtsev, problematic questions asked by the students themselves are of particular importance, with the help of which you can not only find out what the student knows but also tell about the depth, breadth, and level of mental development of his knowledge [6].

The problem of learning consists of theoretical and practical difficulties, which result from the student's research activities.

Problematic questions and problematic tasks cause problematic situations in the minds of students.

This is one of the basic concepts of theory under discussion.

The solution of methods for the psychological and pedagogical design of problematic situations ensures the complete organization of cognitive and creative activities of students. In the concept of "A way to solve problem situations," which stands in the main row of the theory of problem-based learning, the assimilation of indicative information is based on the specifics of subject restructuring and the activities of students in conducting research while mastering the program material. The concept of "a way to solve problem situations" is used similarly to "A way of mental activity." Problem-based learning can be ineffective in certain situations. As practice shows, the process of problem-based learning generates various levels, such as intellectual complexity and cognitive activity of students; a student's cognitive independence may be very high or absent altogether.

In connection with this evidence, an attempt is made to identify the types of problem-based learning. It is more correct to distinguish the types of problem-based learning from the corresponding types of creativity. D. V. Vilkeev classifies three types of problem-based learning:

- The first type – ("scientific" creativity) involves theoretical research, the search and finding of new definitions, laws, and theorems by the student. This type of problem-based learning is based on solving and constructing theoretical learning tasks.

- The second type (practical creativity) involves the search for practical solutions, the application of unknown knowledge in new situations, methods of construction, inventions.

- The third type (artistic creativity) is a manifestation of authentic creativity based on creative representation. It consists of works of literature, drawing, and writing musical works.

Features of problem-based teaching methods and the effectiveness of their application. The method of monological training. Signs: verbal presentation of educational material by the teacher, explanatory description of arguments, the accidental occurrence of problematic situations. Main functions:

- Bringing ready-made conclusions of science to students in the form of evidence, laws, procedures, and situations;

- Organization of repetition and assimilation of the material studied, deepening of knowledge;

- Improvement of reproductive thinking [7].

Usage: monological methods are used in the form of lectures, employing techniques such as conversation, description of arguments, demonstration of phenomena, mentioning, quoting. This method involves the activities of students: observation, listening, memorization, responding to a sample, working with tables, tools, solving typical tasks.

The dialog method. Main features: presentation of educational materials in the form of a narrative message used by students on the basis of reproductive questions based on known materials. The teacher can set one set of problematic tasks and create problematic situations,

but in this case, the teacher explains the meaning of new concepts and ways of action. Main functions:

- To reveal new concepts and methods of educational activity with the help of pre-prepared problem situations and reproductive issues;
- Activation of cognitive attitude and awakening of practical activity of students and mental activity;
- Formation of speech abilities and personal functions of students;
- Teaching students how to think collectively.

A heuristic method. The main signs:

- the teacher's organization of the learned educational material in the form of a heuristic conversation;
- statement of problematic issues;
- solving cognitive tasks;

Learning issues are raised and resolved with the help of a teacher. Main functions:

- personal assimilation of knowledge and methods of action;
- development of creative thinking;
- to see new signs of the studied object;
- transformation of well-known methods of activity and creation of new individual approaches;
- development of mental qualities, thinking skills, formation of cognitive abilities;
- teaching students the ways of active cognitive communication;
- develop motivation to learn and motivation to achieve goals.

The research method. Main features: the teacher organizes individual work on the study of new knowledge, gives them tasks of a problematic nature, and, connecting with them, determines the purpose of the work. Problematic situations arise during the execution of tasks by students in order, which are usually theoretical and practical in nature.

Main functions:

- forms creative thinking and other ideas that make up the intellectual sphere;
- students learn knowledge and ways of doing things individually;
- stimulating the emergence of new ways of acting that are not trained in advance, the formation of motivational, emotional and volitional spheres.

An algorithmic method. The main signs:

- oral education of students;
- demonstration of algorithm execution and action models;
- availability of templates and algorithmic services.

Main functions:

- the formation of students' skills to work with certain disciplines and prescriptions, the organization of laboratory and practical work as directed.
- formation of flexibility in the individual construction of a new activity algorithm.

Using the algorithmic method of teaching, the teacher gets the opportunity to show ready-made options for actions that he gives in judgment, teaches the algorithm of actions, teaches their construction, teaches the formation of flexibility and skills of practical performing services.

The programmed method. Main features: machine

and non-machine programming of training materials in the construction of questions.

Main functions:

- control using programmed pedagogical tools;
- self-management skills training;
- computer skills training;
- compilation of training and other computer programs.

Since problem-based learning is used in the structure of other methods, it cannot be considered as a unique way of learning and a new learning system. Ideally, it should be considered as a special approach to the organization of training.

We purposefully apply problem-based learning in the following cases:

1. The content of the educational material aimed at the formation of concepts, laws, theories consists of a causal relationship and dependence.
2. Students are ready for problem-based learning of the topic.
3. Students complete tasks to develop skills such as personal thinking, the formation of research flexibility, and an approach to work in a creative way.
4. The teacher has time for a problematic study of the topic.
5. The teacher is well versed in the appropriate teaching method.

Features of the problem-based learning methodology. Let's look at the features of the problem-based learning methodology. The provision of educational services using current methods carries not only informativeness, but also the desire to achieve a sustainable understanding of students. The purpose of problem-based learning is to develop a system of thinking, not limited to the superficial performance of tasks, but allowing students to solve complex problems in the context of a system of assessment and understanding of the level of learning. These characteristics allow students to actively analyze, compare, synthesize and obtain new information in the learning process.

D.S. Lyudmilov, E.A. Dyshinsky, A.M. Lurie describe the following characteristics of the problem-based learning methodology.

The first and most important feature is the systematic development of knowledge, its breadth, depth and structuring, as well as the stimulation of intuitive and logical-theoretical thinking of students in the process of solving educational tasks.

The second feature is the availability of an effective tool for structuring problem-based learning. The process of problem-based learning is determined by didactic, practical and critical characteristics. The successful solution of problematic tasks by students depends on certain conditions that promote conscious perception and evaluation of information.

The third feature is the identification of the relationship between theoretical and practical problems, as well as an indication of the importance of correctly assessing the relationship between learning and real life based on didactic principles. Establishing a connection with real life contributes to efficiency in solving life situations and evaluating the correctness of solving educational problems.

The fourth feature is the organization of various types and types of independent work of students within the framework of using the methodology of problem-based learning. The teacher uses this feature to structure individual works that require students to do their own research and generalize their knowledge.

The fifth feature is the phenomenon of serpendilia in the methodology of problem-based learning. The serpentine methodology of problem-based learning follows dialectical laws, which are based on the natural transition of one phenomenon into another.

The fifth feature is determined by its didactic principle of independent approach. Individualization in problem-based learning is mainly justified by the presence of learning problems of varying complexity, different construction. At the same time, problems are perceived differently by each student, in turn, this situation contributes to the search for various hypotheses and other ways of proving.

The sixth feature of problem-based learning is its dynamism. With the dynamism of problem-based learning based on the interrelation of dialectical law, one situation naturally turns into another.

As shown by Yu. K. Babansky, N.v. Basova, W. Okon, M. N. Skatkin and others, there is no dynamism in traditional education, in which degree prevails.

The seventh feature was the high emotional activity of the student. Firstly, the problematic situation is the source of emotional activity, and secondly, the active mental activity of the student must be continuously connected with the sensory–emotional sphere of mental activity.

The eighth feature of problem-based learning is that it provides a new ratio of induction and deduction,

a new reproductive and productive ratio of students, and creative assimilation of knowledge.

As a result, it turns out that the first feature of problem-based learning provides the strength of knowledge and a special type of thinking, the second—the depth of beliefs, the third—the creative application of knowledge in life.

These three features are of great public importance and ensure the fulfillment of basic tasks in educational institutions. And the remaining five features are socially didactic in nature and are based on the effectiveness of the first three [8].

The effectiveness of the problem-based learning method. One or another form of problem-based learning Shamova T. I. speaks about the need to apply in the following cases:

1. The content of the educational material includes a causal relationship and dependence;
2. Students are ready for problem-based learning.;
3. students solve tasks for the formation of research flexibility and the development of independent thinking;
4. the teacher has time for a problematic study of the topic;
5. The teacher is well versed in the appropriate teaching method [9].

The level of effectiveness of problem-based learning reflects the process of students mastering new topics and ways of mental activity. It is characterized by the independent activity of the student in the preparation of tasks and their solution, the level of assimilation of knowledge [10].

The level of effectiveness of problem-based learning can be determined by the ability to use the so-called "research method" of learning.

Table 1. Student and teacher activities in problem-based and traditional learning.

So, summing up the above, we can draw the following conclusions: the use of elements of problem-based learning, taking into account its specific features, various types and levels, allows us to solve the following tasks:

- To regulate the independence and activity of students
- , cognitive difficulties while sitting can be raised by overcoming;
- development of cognitive motives;
- providing students with the ability to apply acquired knowledge in new situations;
- strengthening of general academic and subject abilities;
- providing deep, strong, conscious knowledge;
- formation of logical-theoretical and intuitive thinking;
- implementation of individualization and differentiation of learning;
- to promote the development and emergence of creative abilities;

Below is a table of the activities of students and teachers in problem-oriented and traditional learning.

The main conditions for the effective use of problem-based learning: problem situations should meet the goals of building a knowledge system, be

accessible to students and correspond to their cognitive abilities, cause independent cognitive activity and activity, be able to independently find uncertainty and analyze problems, and not solve problems based on acquired knowledge. The advantages of problem-based learning: increasing students' independence, forming motivation for independence or cognitive interests of students, developing students' mental abilities.

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